

EATING DISORDER IN ADOLESCENCE: BULIMIA NERVOSA

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Eating disorders are psychiatric disorders, which are characterized by serious disturbances in individuals' eating habits. Among them, bulimia nervosa stands out, one of the main concerns in the area of health during adolescence. This disease is identified by repeated episodes of excessive food intake followed by inappropriate compensatory methods

aimed at preventing weight gain. Given the complexity of this disorder, it is essential to understand the risk factors, clinical features, and long-term outcomes associated with bulimia nervosa in adolescence. **OBJECTIVE:** Analysis of the literature on bulimia nervosa in adolescence, in order to provide a comprehensive view on the subject. **METHODOLOGY:** This work is an integrative literature review. A bibliographic survey was carried out through articles in virtual libraries, such as SciELO - Scientific Electronic Library Online, VHL - Virtual Health Library and PUBMED - National Library of Medicine, which address the subject: eating disorders in adolescents - bulimia. The inclusion criteria were: texts available in their complete version, written in Portuguese or English, and that address eating disorders in adolescents, with emphasis on bulimia nervosa. As an exclusion criterion, publications from more than 5 years ago were excluded. **THEORETICAL BACKGROUND:** Bulimia nervosa is an eating disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of binge eating, followed by one or more compensatory behaviors, which aim to avoid caloric gain and occur at least twice a week for at least three months. It peaks at the end of adolescence, has a higher prevalence among young females. It has two forms of presentation: purging type and non-purging type. The clinical picture is composed of systemic symptoms (central nervous system, cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, gastrointestinal tract, endocrine, among others). It is difficult to diagnose. It is associated with biological, psychological and sociocultural factors. Treatment of bulimia nervosa requires a multidisciplinary approach and, in more severe cases, may require hospitalization. **FINAL CONSIDERATIONS:** Bulimia nervosa is an eating disorder that negatively impacts the physical and mental health of adolescents, whose early diagnosis can prevent the development of future complications. This work discusses bulimia nervosa in order to explain about this pathology in adolescents, to avoid negative outcomes. This article also aims to contribute as an input for the current database and for future scientific research and to encourage discussions about this extremely relevant topic.

Keywords: Bulimia. Mental health. Teenager.

INTRODUCTION

Eating behavior disorders (ED) are psychiatric disorders characterized by serious disturbances in individuals' eating habits, which in advanced stages can lead to death. Worldwide, they affect more than 30 million people and are commonly underdiagnosed and undertreated, which makes screening essential (AQUINO; BRAZ; OLIVEIRA, 2023; ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021).

Due to the current beauty standard, the prevalence of these disorders is increasing among female adolescents, which makes them a public health problem. Among BAD, bulimia nervosa (BN) stands out, one of the main concerns in the health area, especially during adolescence (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021; PEREIRA; COSTA; AOYAMA, 2020).

Bulimia nervosa is identified by repeated episodes of excessive food intake followed by inappropriate compensatory methods, such as inducing oneself to vomit, abusing laxatives, prolonged periods of fasting or compulsive involvement in physical activities. These behaviors

aim to avoid weight gain and maintain the desired body appearance and are often accompanied by intense feelings of guilt and shame (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021).

Given the complexity of this disorder, it is essential to understand the risk factors, clinical characteristics and long-term outcomes associated with bulimia nervosa in adolescence. Furthermore, it is essential to identify effective prevention and intervention strategies to help young people deal with challenges related to eating and body image.

In this context, this literature review aims to explore and analyze the most recent research on bulimia nervosa in adolescence, in order to provide a comprehensive view on the topic, considering that the understanding of eating disorders has evolved over time, as well such as diagnostic, treatment and prevention approaches.

METHODOLOGY

This work is an integrative literature review. For its preparation, a bibliographic survey was carried out using articles in virtual libraries that address the subject: eating disorders in adolescents - bulimia.

The documents for reading and analysis were selected from a search in virtual libraries, such as: SciELO – *Scientific Electronic Library Online* , VHL – Virtual Health Library and PUBMED – *National Library of Medicine* , using the following descriptors: bulimia, mental health, adolescent and eating disorders.

The inclusion criteria were texts available in their full version, written in Portuguese or English, and that address eating disorders in adolescents, with an emphasis on bulimia nervosa. As an exclusion criterion, publications from more than 5 years ago were excluded.

After defining the articles, according to the selected inclusion and exclusion criteria, the following steps were followed: exploratory reading, selective reading and election of articles to be used, following the purposes and theme of this review, and, finally, the writing of the final article.

The present study was carried out exclusively with secondary data, publicly accessible, without identifying the subjects, complying with the ethical principles of resolution 196/96 of the National Health Council, which justifies the absence of the opinion of the Research Ethics Committee (CEP) .

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Bulimia Nervosa (BN)

Bulimia nervosa is an eating disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of binge eating, followed by one or more compensatory behaviors, such as: self-induced vomiting, excessive use of laxatives or intense physical exercise. These compensation mechanisms aim to avoid caloric gain and occur at least twice a week for at least three months and can cause serious physical and psychological consequences (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021) .

Epidemiology

Lifetime prevalence rates for bulimia nervosa ranged from 0.3% to 4.6% in women and from 0.1% to 1.3% in men. This pathology occurs worldwide in individuals of all ages, although it has a highest prevalence peak between 15-29 years old (VAN EEDEN; VAN HOEKEN; HOEK, 2021).

Classification

This disorder has two forms of presentation: purging type and non-purging type. The first type involves medication abuse (laxatives, sedatives and enemas) and progresses to the stage of self-induced vomiting during the BN episode. In the non-purgative form, the individual resorts to compensatory mechanisms, such as fasting and excessive physical activity, but does not use drugs or involve vomiting (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021) .

Clinical picture and diagnosis

The repercussions of these behaviors are evidenced by problems in the central nervous system (emotional dysregulation), in the cardiovascular system (electrolyte imbalance and its repercussions), in the musculoskeletal system (growth retardation), in the gastrointestinal tract (esophageal lesions), in the endocrine system (disorders hormonal and thyroid diseases), among others (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021) .

As the symptoms are not specific and people with the disease generally do not reveal that they carry out compensatory practices, the diagnosis is usually mistaken or delayed, which leads to a worsening of the patient's condition (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021) .

Associated factors

In adolescence, bulimia nervosa presents some specific characteristics, as these individuals are going through a phase of development and transition, in which they face significant physical, emotional and social changes. These changes act as predisposing factors for the development of eating disorders, including bulimia nervosa (PEREIRA; COSTA; AOYAMA, 2020) .

It is understood that several factors, internal and external, can contribute to the emergence of BN in adolescence. Among them, biological factors stand out, such as genetic predisposition, neurochemical dysregulation and hormonal changes. Furthermore, psychological factors, such as low self-esteem, perfectionism, dissatisfaction with body image and emotional regulation problems, also play an important role (MORAES *et al* , 2021).

The influence of sociocultural standards, which value extreme thinness and promote unrealistic ideals of beauty, is another relevant factor in the development of this eating disorder in adolescence. Social pressure, weight-related *bullying* and exposure to idealized body images can contribute to the development of body image distortions and harmful eating behaviors (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021).

Treatment

Treatment of bulimia nervosa in adolescence generally requires a multidisciplinary approach. Involving a team made up of doctors, psychiatrists, psychologists and nutritionists, the treatment seeks to address the physical and psychological aspects of the disorder. BN is treated with combined individual therapy, family therapy, behavior modification, and nutritional rehabilitation. Cognitive-behavioral therapy is a commonly used approach and has demonstrated effectiveness in treating the disease (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021; PEREIRA, 2020) .

It is important to highlight that bulimia nervosa can have serious complications and, in more serious cases, it is up to the nutritionist and psychiatrist responsible for the case to decide on hospitalization (if uncontrolled purging, very serious medical complications, psychosis, self-

harm, for example). Therefore, early detection and adequate diagnosis and treatment are essential to minimize health risks and promote the recovery of adolescents (ALMEIDA & CARDOSO, 2021; AQUINO; BRAZ; OLIVEIRA, 2023).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Eating disorders have a clinical diagnosis. Among these disorders is bulimia nervosa, which can be identified through a primary assessment. When recognized early, it is extremely important to direct the patient to appropriate treatment, which includes: psychotherapy, monitoring with a nutritionist and psychiatrist and ensuring a support network.

Bulimia nervosa is an eating disorder that negatively impacts the physical and mental health of adolescents. Current literature shows that when identified early, through its clinical picture, the development of future complications can be avoided.

This work discusses bulimia nervosa in adolescents as a way of explaining the concept of this pathology, its manifestations, clinical picture and complications, diagnosis, predisposing factors and treatment of this pathology in adolescents, in order to avoid negative outcomes, as well as encouraging early diagnoses. This article also aims to contribute as input to the current database and for future scientific research and to encourage discussions about this extremely relevant topic.

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